

Evaluate the effects of customized interventions on parent's ability to deal a child with congenital adrenal hyperplasia.

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ABSTRACT: Background: Congenital adrenal Hyperplasia (CAH) is a serious endocrine disorder which runs in families in an autosomal recessive manner. It is a group of disorders in which there is a defect in cortisol production. Material& methods: Quasi-experimental two group study (Control & interventional) group was used. Study was conducted at Fatima memorial Hospital Lahore. Purposive sampling technique was used on 110 parents equally divided into two groups. Data was collected through Parents' ability assessment questionnaire. Interventions were given by teaching and providing booklet regarding disease management. Results: Comparison of Pre & Post ability Categories of control group majority of parents were mothers (90.9%, n=50) had poor ability in care of child with CAH in pre intervention scores which remained almost the same without any intervention after the 4 months (87.3%, n=48). Interventional group results revealed a significant change (92.7%, n=51) with p value ($p < 0.005$). After 4 months of educational interventions parents had good ability to care a child with CAH while results were very poor (0%, n=0%) in parents without any intervention.

Conclusion: conclusion of the study was that parents who received educational interventions their children had good quality of life and in return their repeated hospital admission was also reduced.

Recommendations: Retrospective studies should be conducted to analyses previous data. Sample size should be greater as many parents refuse to give data so study takes more time to collect the data. Study settings should be diverse to compare the post data results in different settings.

Keywords: Congenital adrenal Hyperplasia (CAH), Parents ability Sick day, customized interventions.

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1. Introduction

A congenital disorder is a condition that is present in children from birth. (1). There are various causes of congenital disorders; they could be genetic or environmental. (2) These disorders have a great impact on a child's health status. (3). One of the serious endocrine congenital disorders is congenital adrenal hyperplasia (CAH) which runs in families in an autosomal recessive manner. (4). In congenital adrenal hyperplasia, five enzymes are responsible for the biosynthesis of cortisol from cholesterol in the adrenal cortex. (5).

21-hydroxylase (21OHD) is responsible for genetic mutation and accounts for 90-95% of cases of CAH and also accounts for the impaired synthesis of cortisol as well as excessive production of androgen (sex hormone). (6). Congenital adrenal hyperplasia is one of the important factors of adrenal crises like vomiting, loose motion, failure to thrive, severe infections and shock due to electrolyte imbalance.(7). With this adrenal insufficiency patient need continuous use of steroids once or twice a day cross sectional observational study was conducted between the periods of 2005 to 2019 in Ireland the calculated prevalence of CAH was 1:14,754 or 0.07 cases per 1,000 live births annually. (8). This disease can affect various components of life and can impair normal quality of life of children. If child has sex ambiguity all these domains are affected and lead to discomfort, state of not being well and dissatisfaction from life. (9) A cross sectional observational study results revealed that the calculated prevalence of CAH was 1:14,754 or 0.07 cases per 1,000 live births annually. (10)

Families having children with CAH have poor knowledge regarding awareness and education about CAH management. (11). For this purpose a Cross-sectional study was conducted in Indonesia with an aim of family educational strategies about management of children with CAH. Study results revealed 14.28% of parents did not know about adjustment of drug doses during sick periods. 21.42% respondents showed low understanding about routine drugs. Literature revealed that timely treatment, education about disease and counseling of families having children with CAH are very essential. (Lestari, 2020). A longitudinal survey was conducted in 2021 in University of Glasgow, Glasgow With aim of analyzing clinical factors associated with adrenal crises and episodes of sick day's results showed incidence of adrenal crises in children with CAH per year was 5.2-10.9 per person per year and incidence of sick day was 67 per 100 patients per year. (12). False perceptions, poor knowledge and ability of parents to manage the child, affect the child physical, psychological, and social health and quality of life of children with CAH. (Siebere,R 2020) According to a longitudinal study conducted to see the effect of education about health related quality of life of a children with CAH parents of children's show great interest during teaching sessions and express their feelings that information provided by health care team were very beneficial in caring a children in period of severe illness specially training about administration of injection solocartif shorts during period of sick days to manage crises situation at home. (13).

Limitations of the study: Indoor patients should be included in the study. Study was limited to only one type of CAH other types should be focused in future studies. Parents feel hesitate to give data because of children sex ambiguity researcher face great difficulty in data collection and during educational interventions.

Problem Statement: To assess parent's ability to deal a child with Congenital Adrenal hyperplasia was very understudied topic in research. (14) In this disease, children suffer from different problems.(15) Which could result in severe complications like vomiting 61.1% (n = 196), diarrhoea (24.4%, n = 19) dehydration, Hyperkalemia, 17.3%, n = 14), shock 4.1% with shock and even death.(16). Children with CAH having great risk of morbidity and mortality and with sever adrenal crises which are estimated between 4.9 and 10 adrenal crises per 100 patients per year. (17). Current study was focused on education of parents to improve their ability to deal a child with CAH. Objective: To evaluate the effects of customized interventions on parent's ability to deal a child with congenital adrenal hyperplasia.

2. Methods

Two group quasi-Experimental study design was selected to achieve the study objectives. In two groups study, one group was interventional group (group 1) and other was control group (group 2). Sample size of 50 cases in each group was calculated with

95% confidence level, 80% power of the test and expected percentage of quality of life of children with congenital adrenal hyperplasia in control group as 16% and in experimental group as 33% (Sadik, 2019).

After adding 10% dropout rate the sample size was 55 (110 cases in each group). The sample size was calculated using the following formula:

Please select the desired unknown:

Level of significance (%)

Power of the test (%)

Anticipated population proportion 1

Anticipated population proportion 2

Sample size

Please enter the remaining values:

α

$1 - \beta$

P_1

P_2

n

$$n = \frac{\left\{ z_{1-\alpha/2} \sqrt{2\bar{P}(1-\bar{P})} + z_{1-\beta} \sqrt{P_1(1-P_1) + P_2(1-P_2)} \right\}^2}{(P_1 - P_2)^2}$$

Parents of newly diagnosed cases of congenital adrenal hyperplasia were selected in study by using purposive sampling technique. Children with other endocrine disorders, like Diabetes insipid, Cushing Syndrome, short stature, Hypothyroidism/Hyperthyroidism were excluded from the study. Data was collected systematically in three phases. In pre-interventional phase which started after ethical approval for the study from the university of Lahore (Letter Ref No: REC-UOL_415-05-2023) that was issued on dated May 25th, 2023. After that approval was taken from the hospital administration in written form and then from Head of the department before approaching to the study participants. Secondly, written informed consent was signed from the study participants. Data was collected from the study participants by using questionnaire regarding parent's Ability Containing 22 questions in first month established by the researcher after checking reliability by cronbach alpha (0.172) and validity from 5 experts of endocrine department. Initially pre data was taken from both groups (control & interventional). Each group was consisted of 55 participants. In 2nd phase which was interventional phase of 4 months parents who received interventions (Education about disease) by providing a booklet regarding ability and taking care of the children with CAH which in return improve their quality of life. One to one teaching session of 30-35 minutes was arranged for interventional group parents in endocrine OPD room during their visit in endocrine OPD on two days in a week, 6 to 8 parents on each day (13+14+14+14). Later 3months teaching was given through whatsapp group created for the study participants, purpose of that whatsapp group was to remain in contact and educate the participants and resolve the quires of the participants according to their need by sharing teaching stuff, disease management strategies and sick day management of the CAH. In post interventional phase data was collected to see the improvement in parent's ability to take care of their child with CAH. Later data was analysed on SPSS version 25.0 by using descriptive (frequency & percentages) and inferential statistics (Wilcoxon signed rank and mann-whitney U test) test to compare pre & post data among parents.

Table: 2 Demographic Characteristics of Parents of Children with CAH

Demographic Characteristics	Control Group		Interventional Group	
	f	%	f	%
Father	18	32.7%	11	20.0%
Mother	37	67.3%	44	80.0%
Parent/caregiver age				
25-<30	12	21.8%	16	29.1%
30-<35	27	49.1%	31	56.4%
35-<40	12	21.8%	7	12.7%
Parent/caregiver Education	Control group			
Primary	26	47.3%	22	40.0%
Elementary	13	23.6%	19	34.5%
Secondary	9	16.4%	10	18.2%
University	7	12.7%	4	7.3%

Table 2. Revealed that female parents were greater in number in both groups control group (67.3%, n=37) and in interventional group (80.0% n= 44) as compare to the male parents in both groups control group (32.7% n= 18) and interventional group (20.0%, n=11). In age groups parents were greater in number 30-<35 (56.4%, n=31) interventional group as compare to (49.1%, n=27) in control group. Most of parents were in primary level in control group (47.3%, n= 26) as compare to the parents of interventional group (40%, n= 22) with respect to other levels (elementary, secondary, university).

Table: 3 Comparison of Pre and Post Ability Categories of Control (n=55) & Intervention group. (n=55)

Categories	Control Group		Intervention Group	
	Pre Ability f (%)	Post Ability f (%)	Pre Ability f (%)	Post Ability f (%)
Poor ability score (< 11)	50 (90.9%)	48 (87.3%)	47 (85.5%)	0 (0%)
Average Ability score range from 11-16.5	5 (9.1%)	7 (12.7%)	8 (14.5%)	4 (7.3%)
Good Ability score (>16.5)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	51 (92.7%)

Table 5. Comparison of Parents ability scores before and after the intervention (Control & Intervention Groups)

Variables	Control Group Median I(QR)		P value	Intervention Group		P value
	Pre	Post		Pre	Post	
Parents Ability	5 (4)	5 (3)	> 0.570	6 (4)	17 (1)	< 0.001

Table 3 Showed the Comparison of Pre and Post Ability Categories of Control and Intervention group. Results revealed that most of parents (90.9%, n=50) had poor ability in care of child with congenital adrenal hyperplasia in pre intervention scores which remained almost the same without any intervention after the 4 months (87.3%, n=48). Interventional group results revealed a significant change (92.7%, n=51) after 4 months of educational

interventions, parents had good ability to care a child with CAH while results were very poor (0%, n=0%) in parents without any intervention.

Table 5 showed the analysis of pre and post ability scores among parent in the control group, the median pre scores were median 5 (IQR 4) which was almost similar to the post ability scores median 5 (IQR 3) of the parents who did not receive any intervention (p value > 0.570.). Whereas, in the analysis of pre and post ability scores among parents in the intervention group, the median pre scores were 6. (IQR 4) Which significantly improved after the four months of intervention median 17(IQR 1) hence it is proved that there is a significant difference in pre and post interventional scores of parents who received the intervention (p value <0.001).

Table 6. Comparison of Parents post intervention ability score (Control & Intervention Groups)

Variables	Control Group	Intervention Group	P value
	Post Median (IQR)	Post Median (IQR)	
Parents Ability	5 (3)	17 (1)	< 0.001

Table 6 In the analysis of post ability scores among parent in the control group, and intervention group the median scores of control; group median was 5 (IQR 3) which significantly improved after the four months of intervention in interventional group post intervention median was 17 (IQR 1) hence it is proved that there is a significant difference in post interventional scores of parents who received the intervention (p value <0.001).

3. Discussion

In analysis of pre and post ability scores among parents in the control group, the median pre scores were median 5 (IQR 4) which was almost similar to the post ability scores median 5 (IQR 3) of the parents who did not receive any intervention (p value > 0.570.).

These findings are similar with the study conducted by (1) Health and Quality of Life Outcomes, who discussed that child had poor quality of life whose parents don't learn about the disease and its management strategies which result in great loss.

Another study (2) supports the results of current study that half of parents (50%) were not able to manage the disease because they had proper knowledge about how to manage the disease (CAH).

Whereas, in the analysis of pre and post ability scores among parents in the intervention group, the median pre scores were 6. (IQR 4) Which significantly improved after the four months of intervention median 17(IQR 1) hence it is proved that there is a significant difference in pre and post interventional scores of parents who received the intervention (p value <0.005).

As discussed in the study conducted by (Musa, 2020). Study results concluded that parental education is necessary to manage the symptoms of disease during period of severe illness to avoid extra fatigue of hospitalization. (p =0.001).

(3) in their study management of CAH during preconception, pregnancy and postpartum also supports the current research that parents who had proper knowledge and understanding about management of CAH and also steroid dose adjustment had significant improvement (p<0.005) in management of their child health.

Analysis of post ability scores among parents in the control group, and intervention group the median scores of control; group median was 5 (IQR 3) which significantly improved after the four months of intervention in interventional group post intervention median was 17 (IQR 1).

These results highly consistent with the study conducted by Borhani et al., (2011), according to this study educational interventions are integral part of family education regarding best management of adrenal crises and to improve overall quality of life of children hence current study proved that there is a significant difference in post interventional scores of parents who received the intervention (p value <0.005).

Another study also supports these results that there was great association ($p=0.002$) between knowledge and of mothers of children with CAH. (4)

4. Conclusion

This study results revealed that before interventions parents had poor knowledge and were not able to take care their children so their children had poor quality of life but after 4 months of educational interventions showed good ability to manage their children and their children had good quality of life. Hence it is proved that education and awareness about disease can improve quality of life of children with congenital adrenal hyperplasia.

5. Recommendations

Retrospective studies should be conducted to analyses previous data. Sample size should be greater as many parents refuse to give data so study takes more time to collect the data. Study settings should be diverse to compare the post data results in different settings.

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